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Article

Impact of Coronavirus & Development (DoD) in China

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Abstract: CoronaVirus (COVID-19) won't be discussed once again because it has gained worldwide attention now. Some countries have decided to call it 'China Virus' as well. The topic of discussion here is DoD which implies Development over Disaster in China. In this article the impact of some precautionary measures and steps are shown and some positive points with higher possibilities in the sustainable development of China will be discussed. The goal of this article is to show some possibilities which may impact the vast majority of development in China. Socio-economic Development has been impacted during this disaster period. Determining the production possibility and possible movement in industrial and socio-economic development is a key factor to focus on at the moment.

Keywords: COVID19, Coronavirus, Economic Development, Development Engineering, Wuhan

Introduction

Coronavirus which was scientifically named COVID-19 by the International Nomenclature of disease, has become the latest buzzword in the world. Coronaviruses are zoonotic, meaning they are transmitted between animals and people. To reduce the impact of the new coronavirus, the government of China together with the people have taken enough measures to deal with the situation. The measures were hard and harsh but the situation has been properly handled and everything was under control. In short this devastating occurrence which should have crippled the economy of China is rather transforming the future of the nation.

Socio-Economic Development Impact: The possible impact and related factors are hereby described. The relevant fields of sustainable development and possible outcomes are reflected as well. Not only is China facing a challenge, but also the whole world is experiencing the effect. The

Chinese manufacturing chain is directly or indirectly linked to a big part of world economies, so it's just upsetting the whole chain. **National Development:** All schools in china, from preschool to tertiary institutions, have been instructed to temporarily suspend classes to prevent gatherings so that it will be easier to contain the outbreak. However the Ministry of Education have put out a directive for schools to continue teaching via the internet using the online platforms provided by the government. This is a huge milestone in the age of internet. This difficult moment is transforming the future of the nation. The critical moment is helping the whole teachers' nation to turn to an online host within a short time. The students are adapting to technological era as well. Unlimited demand always creates quicker production what's are expected in the field of sustainable development. The development won't be bound in national demand or national supply but to international supply chain as well.

E-commerce movement: Most of the major workplaces including some restaurants, chain stores and factories in the cities have also been instructed to stop operating to avoid gatherings. As a result business has shifted to the e-commerce platform with Alibaba and other e-commerce giants leading the way in the transformation of the Chinese e-commerce industry. Delivery services especially food delivery services were beginning to pick up pace before the outbreak but the epidemic has led to almost 97% business shift from door to door or person to person to online transaction.

Implementation of state of the art technology: The process of implementing state of the art technology for use in daily life has been quite slow but a significant portion of the features have been implemented in a short period of time. Artificial Intelligence, has been employed to diagnose, analyze and monitor the transmission rate of the virus. These features are not commonly used in the medical field to fight against sudden outbreaks but during this coronavirus outbreak these features have been quickly developed and swiftly implemented. Body temperature can be checked using close circuit camera which is as amazing as it is surprising. Using 'robot nurses' to attend to infected patients significantly reduces the spread of the virus. This is certainly new to the 70's generation.

Industrial transformation: Within a short period of time, quite a large number of factories have switched their business model in terms of the products that they now manufacture. The sudden transformation in human resource management must be the best lesson in the section of

manufacturing. Diaper manufacturing companies have switched to the manufacture of mask to protect the public from airborne transmission of the virus when it was needed urgently. China, has for some time now been the world's biggest supplier of various products but recently supply has been disturbed. As a result now is the most appropriate time to implement the 'Industry 4.0 policy and technique'. National scarcity is always a chance to let people adopt within the limit of availability but it also makes producers more creative.

Switch from garments to masks: As soon as the Coronavirus was officially declared an epidemic, many garments industries switched to manufacturing masks. The speed with which they made the switch was very remarkable considering the impromptu nature with which the national emergency was announced. Processes required to start manufacturing must have been a big challenge but somehow it was perfectly handled. The experience will be a positive for Chinese garment industries to maintain the global demand. Maximizing Human Capital appropriately emphasizing Human Development Index (HDI).

Virtualization: Though virtualization is still unknown too much of the world especially second (2nd) and third (3rd) world countries, it has developed rapidly in China. After the outbreak of CoViD-19, the entire people's republic of China was placed under lockdown thus restricting the free flow of goods and services as well as people. IT sectors focused on virtualizing as many services as they could. Museum and Scenic Spot tours were virtualized so that everyone could have a virtual tour to of interesting spots around the country. The main issue of contention was coronavirus prevention but the output was "more than 400,000 imperial artifacts have been virtualized and digitized online". In short it can be said that the biggest virtualization currently known is that which has taken place in China. Not only is the government ensuring the safety of the entire populace, but it is also putting the best effort into ensuring that even during lockdown, the daily lives of the citizens and foreigners remains as close as possible to what it was before the outbreak.

Mobility based services: This category of services almost seemed impossible to provide. This is a period that is very suited to the younger generation as they are virtually tied to their gadgets even before the lockdown, so perhaps the impact of the outbreak on them is relatively insignificant compared to the older and less tech savvy generation. A lot of gyms are providing live-telecasting work-out platforms. Just turning some associated apps gyms are becoming available in home.

Ministry of Education offered Educational lessons on education centered TV channels and open source education platforms which can be considered as an indirect implementation of 5G network in real life. “Stop production to ensure safety, Start production to maximize comfort & happiness. These two factors are mutually conflicting but Chinese manufacturers are expected to deal it properly.” is properly reflected here.

Global Transportation: Due to the coronavirus outbreak, quite a number of airline companies have cancelled flights to and from several destinations within and outside China, thus striking a huge blow at the airline industry and eroding a significant margin of the profit that stood to be gained from air travel. The focus was to stop the spread of the Coronavirus, but in the end “China mainland has been able to expand their flights and they are earning more in this critical situation because of lack of flights. The cancellation of numerous flights is an opportunity for China to experience the DaXing Airport which new and big. It’s time to challenge all the challenges and have a good study and prepare for the dynamic development.

Conclusion: Even though the situation is not yet under control, there is more opportunity to transform the nation positively. The situation brought about isolation but indirectly it’s just a more connected, stronger network. Online schooling system implementation is an indirect training for the new generation to adapt to the fifth generation (5G) network. The industries have gained experience and learned lessons from the current epidemic situation. It has become clearly obvious that industry 4.0 policy execution is becoming easier for the whole nation. Development over Disaster (DoD) is really happening in china during the Coronavirus outbreak. The rest is dependent on our nation’s positive attitude and hardworking spirit to develop China with love and care.

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Dedication

The Reason all of our success, our parents. As a Corresponding author I would like to mention the one I loved and was ignored successfully.

Conflicts of Interest

Best wishes for China and we wish China can overcome the situation ASAP. We had a vast study on Possibilities and we tried our best to sort out every point.

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